

WEB BASED CLASSROOM SYSTEM

Tejashree Gurav
KBPCOE Satara

ABSTRACT

One of the changes that the "Information Age" has brought to classrooms is that a Web-Based Classroom Management Support System (WBC) is now required for more efficient classroom management in elementary schools. This research aims at finding desirable Internet uses for more efficient classroom management through designing and implementing a web-based classroom support system. It has been possible to support classroom management beyond the limits of time and space with content found on the web and through guiding learners' internet usage in educational directions utilizing the resources on the web in more academic ways, and when applied in classrooms to help direct learners' active participation developing each learners' own special abilities and aptitudes. A WBC system is expected to offer upgraded classroom management

KEYWORDS: Teacher training; Web-based research; World Wide Web.

INTRODUCTION

While a great deal has been written on the advantage and benefits of online teaching, little is known on how assessment is implemented in online classrooms to monitor and inform performance and progress. The purpose of this study is to investigate the dynamics of Web CT classroom assessment by analyzing the perceptions and experience of the instructors. Grounded theory method was employed to generate a "process theory". The study included 10 faculties who taught Web CT classes, and 216 students in the College of Education in an urban university in the mid west. Interviews and classroom observations were undertaken on line. The findings indicated that, performance-based assessment, writing skills, interactive assessment and learner autonomy were major assessment aspects to inform teaching and enhance learning. If one of the major roles of online instruction is to increase self-directed learning, as part of the pedagogical mechanism, web based classroom assessment should be designed and practiced to impact learner autonomy. The unique features, especially the synchronous and asynchronous communication, web search, online resources and technical support, allow teaching and learning to be place and time independent. Although educators at all levels have embraced using online technology as a teaching tool, the issue of assessment of student learning in an online course has not been thoroughly addressed (Robles & Braathen, 2002).

As an instructional delivery method, online instruction should be designed to facilitate teaching and promote learning. As (Meyer, 2002C) pointed out "It is irrelevant to speak of the effects of using web without understanding how it is entwined with instructional design". As instructors reflect upon online learning as an instructional delivery mechanism, they must

also examine their assessment delivery method. They should ask questions about how assessment practice as part of the instructional design is related to the quality of online teaching.

TECHNOLOGIES

A.OLTP

Find out how SQL Server 2008 provides a scalable, high performance database engine for mission-critical applications that require the highest levels of availability and security, while reducing the total cost of ownership through enhanced enterprise-class manageability.

B.Data Warehousing

It is cover how SQL Server 2008 provides a comprehensive and scalable data warehouse platform that enables organizations to integrate data into the data warehouse faster, scale and manage growing.

C.Wireless Application Protocol (WAP)

Wireless Application Protocol (WAP) is an open international standard for application-layer network communications in a wireless-communication environment. Most use of WAP involves accessing the mobile web from a mobile phone or from a PDA.

A WAP browser provides all of the basic services of a computer-based web browser but simplified to operate within the restrictions of a mobile phone, such as its smaller view screen. Users can connect to WAP sites: websites written in, or dynamically converted to, WML (Wireless Markup Language) and accessed via the WAP browser.

Before the introduction of WAP, service providers had extremely limited opportunities to offer interactive data services, but needed interactivity to support now-commonplace activities such as:

- Email by mobile phone
- Tracking of stock-market prices
- Sports results
- News headlines
- Music downloads

D.Internet Information Server (IIS)

IIS formerly called Internet Information Server - is a set of Internet-based services for servers created by Microsoft for use with Microsoft Windows. It is the world's second most popular

web server in terms of overall websites behind the industry leader Apache HTTP Server. As of April 2009 it served 29.27% of all websites according to Netcraft . The services provided currently include FTP, FTPS, SMTP, NNTP, and HTTP/HTTPS.

MODULES

Home Page:

The two frames divide the page. Firstly left hand side frame has one table containing following items:-

1. About Us: Here this field shows contact details of Web Based Classroom System's developers. If anyone wants to do contact regarding to this web site then about us gives this information.
2. Home: This field gives link to home page. From any page we can go back to the home page, from where student can change his status.
3. Tutor: Tutor field contains the registration form. New tutor can register from this form. It takes details like Tutor Name, Address, Roll whether his roll is student or Tutor, User name, Confirm password, contact, tutors qualification.

Tutor Page:

Tutor: Tutor field contains the registration form. New tutor can register from this form. It takes details like Tutor Name, Address, Roll whether his roll is student or Tutor, User name, Confirm password, contact, tutors qualification.

Using this page tutor record his session or we can say that lectures with various modes like –

Audio: Here tutor will record his lectures verbally so that it will be beneficial for students because many students feel comfortable with this mode rather than to read the notes.

Video: Using this mode, firstly the tutor has to record his session and then this will be saved in this web site. As per students' requirement, the student will choose his comfortable way of learning and get addressed to this mode.

Text: Many students have a fond of reading rather than to watch and listen. The tutor will upload his notes and the student will refer to these uploaded notes.

Student Page:

The screenshot shows a registration form titled "Web Classroom". It includes a "Log In" section with fields for "User Name" and "Password", and a "Remember me next time" checkbox. The main registration section has fields for "Student Name", "Address", "Roll", "User Name", "Password", "Confirm Password", "Contact", and "Class". There are "SUBMIT" and "CANCEL" buttons at the bottom right. A navigation menu on the left includes "ABOUT US", "HOME", "TUTOR", "STUDENTS", and "Sign Out".

New Student's registration can be done using this page.

Student: Student page contains new registration of student and also login page. We provided a facility that student can log in with home page as well as student page also. Student registration form needs details like Student Name, Address, Roll whether he is Student or Tutor, User Name, password, confirm password, contact, class.

How Tutor upload the page?

The screenshot shows the "TUTOR UPLOADING INFORMATION PAGE". It includes a "Log In" section on the left. The main form has fields for "TUTOR NAME" (value: sandeep), "TUTOR SUBJECT" (value: Database), "TUTOR MODE" (value: Video), "RECORD CLASS" (value: Record Class), and "Enter Class Name" (value: mgt). There are "Record Class" and "Stop Record" buttons. A navigation menu on the left includes "ABOUT US", "HOME", "TUTOR", "STUDENTS", and "Sign Out".

Here Tutor uploads the information in three modes:

1. Audio.
2. Video.
3. Text.

Audio: Here tutor will record his lectures verbally so that it will be beneficial for students because many students feel comfortable with this mode rather than to read the notes.

Video: Using this mode, firstly the tutor has to record his session and then this will be saved in this web site. As per students' requirement, the student will choose his comfortable way of learning and get addressed to this mode.

Text: Many students having a fond of reading rather to watch and listen. Tutor will upload his notes and student will refer to these uploaded notes.

Video Capturing:

Using Video mode tutor can record his Video and upload it for Students.

How Student can get the information?

After logged in Student can get information by choosing his required subject, tutor, Various modes such as Video, Audio and Text.

Text Mode:

If Student use Text mode, the text file be opened in this way.

Audio Mode:

If student choose Audio mode, the Audio will play in this way.

Video Mode:

If Student Choose Video mode, the Video will play in this way.

CONCLUSION

Designing web based intelligent tutoring systems is not an easy task. Network latencies must be dealt with, especially if a lot of multimedia (sound, pictures, and animations) is part of the course material. Also, the HTTP protocol is stateless, which is unacceptable for doing student modelling. While solutions to the second problem exist, solutions to the first are still under investigation.

The WEB TUTOR system provides other complications for web-based teaching. First, converting from an already existing lecture course may not be very efficient in terms of creating the domain material. The audio from the class is clearly from lectures, whereas for the on-line version, it should be topic based. It may be better to record audio appropriate for the material rather than taking it from the video tapes.

Second, determining the actions students take is incredibly difficult, since students will not always use the software as intended. Similarly, accurately recording the time spent on the material is not possible, since there is no way to distinguish between idle time and intense studying time.

REFERENCES

[1] *www.google.com*

[2] *www.asp.net*

[3] *www.microsoft.com*

[4] *Microsoft.NET FRAMEWORK 2.0 Web Based Client Development* by Glenn Johnson and Tony Northrup.

[5] P. Brusilovsky, E. Schwarz, and G. Weber. *ELM-ART: An Intelligent Tutoring System on World Wide Web. In Intelligent Tutoring Systems.*

IJIERT